

A Harm-Reduction Approach to Drug-Education Courses in Schools | Survey and Recommendations for Future Implementation

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ABSTRACT

Teen illicit drug use has remained a problem since the early 80s¹, despite alcohol/drug prevention being implemented in the overwhelming majority of high schools. Approaches involving social interaction work better than the ones emphasizing education, and this has been proven repeatedly for at least the past decade. Programs like *D.A.R.E* and the fundamental methodology of health class curriculums have proven ineffective on adolescent drug use. This research article aims to use an array of research and statistical analysis to create a more effective form of drug education and prevention with a harm reductive methodological approach, while still maintaining a form of prevention reinforcement. Past publications have not considered collective feedback from experts, administrators, and students. This research publication intends to combine feedback from all 3 previously mentioned parties to create a new curriculum that will be dominantly focused on harm reduction.

RECOMMENDATION FOR PROPOSED CLASS CURRICULUM

Based on gathered information from students, school administrators, and credentialed professionals, a curriculum base is recommended for a harm-reduction based drug education class. Per harm reduction principles, the curriculum should educate participants on what credible sources say are safe recreational doses of commonly-used drugs, as well as their expected effects (participants should know that the educator is in no way encouraging the use of any recreational drug). Participants should be taught about the importance of the environment for a user, and the proper environment to create. Participants should be taught the history of drug use and curriculum should teach the history of the fight against drugs, including failures, wins, and also current efforts being made toward support-based prevention and support-based interventions (and what characteristics make those programs successful). Participants should be taught that most addicted people are suffering effects from trauma, and they should be taught how to cope with negative emotions. Participants should be talked too by trauma counselors and credentialed professionals (preferably supporters of harm reduction). Participants should not be shielded from from of government wrongs and dishonesty regarding drugs, they should be educated about them in a way that allows students to form trust, as responsibility for dishonesty allows for trust to form. Participants should be taught that the word “drug” refers to all mind-altering substances, even those which are legal (caffeine, cough syrup, etc.). Participants should be taught that it is possible to use drugs in a controlled responsible way, and that the recreational use of mind-altering substances does not necessarily constitute abuse, however, it should be made clear that moderation isn’t a “cure” and will not eliminate the possibility of long-term harm/undesirable effects. Moderation instead reduces the probability of short and long term harm. Educators must be informed that nothing is more crucial regarding safe drug use then the relevant context, the danger posed by recreational use of most drugs is the pharmacology and dosage of the drug, the psychological state of the user at the time of use, and the setting.

INTRODUCTION

In 2016, 86% of high schools, 79.7% of middle schools, and 63.9% of elementary schools required “alcohol or other drug-use prevention” in their health policies (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016). Despite alcohol and drug prevention health policies being present in most schools across the United States, recent research suggests that prevention-based policies are ineffective. The illicit drug use rate among 8th, 10th, and 12th-grade students has remained within a 4% margin since 2003 (Johnston et al., 2019).

Two decades of data indicates D.A.R.E and programs similar to it are almost entirely ineffective on the probability participating students will use illicit drugs. A 5-year longitudinal study found a slight increase in drug use among students who took part in D.A.R.E compared to students who didn’t (Clayton, Cattarello, & Johnstone, 1996). More recent and much larger analytical studies have revisited D.A.R.E’s effectiveness—results also firmly indicated no reduction on the probability participants would engage in illicit drug use. (West & O’Neal, 2004).

Given that in 2016, 86% of high schools required alcohol or other drug use prevention, combined with the fact that illicit drug use among 8th, 10th, and 12th graders has remained relatively unchanged for over a decade, a conclusion can be made: the current approach to adolescent drug education is ineffective. Respectively, there’s been innovative research into effective methods of adolescent drug education and prevention, such improvements have yet to be

implemented on a mass scale, and adolescent drug use continues to stay on a straight trend, moving slightly upward in recent years (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2016; Johnston et al., 2019; Tobler, 1986). This article aims to compile research from various recent studies, school administrator feedback, student feedback, as well as the constructive feedback of credentialed professionals that have experience/knowledge of drug use and addiction to make a propositional course with a strong bias toward harm reduction rather than drug prevention based.

BRIEF LITERATURE REVIEW

Multiple studies have shown that harm reduction approaches to drug education are more beneficial to that of prevention. One study collected data on students of a class that had a harm reduction approach with alcohol in a drug-education setting, and the results found intervention students consumed about 31% less alcohol. 17 months after the program, intervention students were at most 33% less likely to drink “risky” levels of alcohol. Intervention students experienced an average of about 21% less alcohol-caused harm (McBride, Farrington, Midford, Meuleners, & Phillips, 2004).

Another study on the effectiveness of harm reduction intervention concluded that “screening and brief intervention are efficacious, but efficacy of a range of treatment approaches has not been reliably established. Harm-reduction interventions are effective in young people involved in risky and injecting substance use”

(Toumbourou et al., 2007). Another publication makes the thesis that harm-reduction drug-education programs are operated on four basic assumptions: “(1) Drugs must be categorized broadly to include all intoxicating substances, including those which are legal. (2) Total abstinence is not realistic. (3) It is possible to use drugs in a controlled responsible way, and the use of mind-altering substances does not necessarily constitute abuse. (4) Perhaps nothing is more crucial regarding safe drug use than context, which comprises the pharmacology and dosage of the drug, the psychological state of the user at the time of use, and the setting”; the same study also says that to reduce drug-related harm in drug-education, relevant risk and benefit of the drug being taught must be included, and a distinction must be made between the “real” and the “imagined” dangers of drugs (Rosenbaum, 1996).

METHODS

The proposal of a harm-reduction based drug education/prevention will be backed by what recent research has shown effective for the target group (9th grade - 12th grade). The proposal must be reasonable (reasonable in terms of district/teacher capability). The proposal will be made using the information given by multiple credentialed individuals that have extensive knowledge and/or publications regarding the subject of adolescent drug use. To ensure a high probability of voluntary student participation, a poll will be given to a local and internet target population that consists of teenagers, ages 13-18. It should be made clear that the proposal will not include any curriculum mandated

given by the Federal or State government, the only curriculum that will be considered is that of the advisory of the county to address specific problems that are known present from student surveys. It is strongly recommended that someone with an established background of adolescent and trauma involvement background teach the class. Teacher’s attitude effects have been proven significant and this is vital to a successful program, and it is strongly advised that if the proposition is studied for effectiveness that teacher attitude is taken into account. Multiple research publications have indicated the connection to the student as a crucial part in drug abuse prevention/early intervention (How, 2014; Perry & Jessor, 1985; Tobler, 1986). All credible/logistical concerns will be taken into account and discussed equally among all those involved. Multiple past/current student drug users will be asked questions about what they would want in the class, these results will be examined for similarities and analyzed for the potentiality of implementation if conditions/circumstances allow and the wants are realistic and considerable beyond a reasonable doubt. The student poll will consist of questions that ask if they have ever used THC based products, opiates, benzodiazepines, or other. It lists options for students to select if they have ever been or are addicted to any of those categories. The poll asks what the student would like to see in a drug education class, the options being: “How addiction works based on recent research”, “Peer to peer support (discussion of personal experiences)”, “Constantly updated curriculum based on research”, “How illicit drugs can be used safely. (Not encouraging drug abuse, but if you use, how to use safely)”, “Learn

valid information about the effects/benefits/disadvantages of illicit drugs”, “How to support your peers yourself”, “Non-government affiliated speakers coming into talk about drugs”, and finally “Seeing both sides of the addiction debate (psychological or physical). The poll will also ask how many addicts the student knows that are under 18, and finally, it asks for final comments and if they would take the class if their previously specified desires were satisfactorily implemented.

RESULTS

A total of 17 poll responses were recorded with ages ranging from 13 to 18 [M=15.8]. The answers to “What would you want to see in a drug education class?” are as follows: 10 [58.8%] of the participants selected “seeing both sides of the addiction debate (Psychological or physical)”; 8 [47.1%] of the participants selected “how addiction works based on recent research”; 7 [41.2%] of the participants selected “peer to peer support (discussion of personal experiences)”; 6 [35.3%] of the participants selected “up-to-date curriculum based on newer research”, “how illicit drugs can be used safely”, and “learn valid information about the effects / benefits / disadvantages of illicit drugs”; 5 [29.4%] or less of the participants selected “how to support your peers yourself”, and “non-government affiliated speakers coming in to talk about drugs”. The answers to “How many addicts do you know that are below the age of 18?” are as follows: 6 [35.3%] of the participants selected “4”; 3 [17.6%] of the participants selected “3”; one participant

said “I know around 5-10 addicts of multiple different substances”, another said “Approx[imately] 7”, another said “10”, another said “around 7-9”, and finally, another said “[A] high amount”. Figure 1 shows the responses to the question “If you have used/been addicted to drugs in the past, what kinds?”. There was a general consensus among the professionals I talked too that trauma education would be an important part of the class. A Trauma Counselor & Behavioral Support Specialist noted that: “The key is bottom up vs. button down. Knowing something doesn’t change [the problem]. You have to give people a new EXPERIENCE... Addiction is a result of Trauma. Period. You can’t change it until you address the trauma.” A High School Counselor also agreed firmly with this. The Chief of Addiction Services at Ohio Mental Health and Recovery Board agreed strongly with the concept and mentioned that their department is seeking funding for harm reduction programs. At the Mental Health and Recovery Board of Union County, of which I visited frequently, there is a very firm consensus that scare tactics do not work and they should not be implemented in any drug education curriculum under any circumstances. School administration consists of general administration, and guidance counselors. The school administration wants some form of prevention backed into curriculum, even if it’s less or changed significantly. They want to make it clear they are not in anyway encouraging the recreational use of drugs. One of the Guidance Counselors noted that if “trauma” is brought into the curriculum in a direct manner, parents may be hesitant

because in general people psychologically uneducated don't understand the meaning of the term "trauma".

DISCUSSION

Survey results, albeit unexpectedly, support a conclusion that most teenagers want to see both sides of the addiction debate. The second conclusion based on survey responses was that teenagers would like to see a scientific explanation of how addiction works in the body in a drug-education class. I theorize that this response is likely a result of the presumption of self-autonomy on behalf of teenagers, that is, they likely assume if they understand addiction, they then have complete autonomy over it. One survey result that was shocking is that only about 18% of participants indicated they would like to learn how to help peers that are going through addiction, this is despite the fact that almost all participants knew of many addicts. This likely means teenagers would rather learn why addiction happens and the structure of it within the body, rather than learning how to help those already addicted. I theorize that the lack of effectiveness in preventionist programs is due to a lack of trust between adolescents and school administration, and I believe that a harm-reduction curriculum in drug education, if taught correctly, has the capacity to repair the relationship between adolescents and their schools. Harm-reduction curriculum would fundamentally be support based, while prevention curriculum always utilizes punishment, consequence, and often fear. Harm-reduction curriculum lacks punishment, consequence, and fear elements, leaving support. I

theorize students will likely subconsciously or consciously notice that the elements that likely are the seed for their distrust have been removed, only allowing room for trust to grow.

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